

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KAVYASHREE bearing USN6SU21PT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
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Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROHITH S NAIR bearing USN6SU21PT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RUSHIKA CHYRMANG bearing USN6SU21PT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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